

ODELIA BREAST MRI Challenge 2025: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

ODELIA BREAST MRI Challenge 2025

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

ODELIA2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Detecting breast cancer early is of the utmost importance to effectively treat the millions of women afflicted by breast cancer worldwide every year. Although mammography (often complemented with ultrasound) is the main imaging modality for screening breast cancer in many countries, there is an increasing interest in adding magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to screening programmes, particularly for women at high risk. Recent guidelines by the European Society of Breast Imaging (EUSOBI) indeed recommended breast MRI as an additional screening tool for women with dense breast tissue. However, analyzing large 3D volumes of MRI scans requires a considerable amount of time from expert radiologists. This highlights the need to develop new automated methods to detect cancer accurately using MRI, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) having the potential to support radiologists in breast MRI interpretation and classification, and to help detect cancer earlier.

The proposed challenge aims to obtain a generalizable algorithm for detecting malignancies in breast MRIs. Challenges for generalizability in real-world data are two-fold. On the one hand, imaging devices and modalities vary between sites, resulting, e.g., in different resolutions. On the other hand, acquisition protocols vary, so that different numbers of scan sequences are taken at different post-contrast time points.

For this purpose, the challenge will involve a dataset consisting of images from six centers in five countries (Germany, UK, Greece, Spain and The Netherlands) acquired with different protocols and vendors, thus representing the variability of a real-world dataset. We will give an example script for pre-processing that encompasses the usual steps expected, namely: splitting the scan into each breast, cropping each half around each breast, normalising voxel intensities. However, we will not be very prescriptive as to how the pre-processing should work as we want teams to come up with their own ideas and we expect that novel solutions for pre-processing of the training dataset will play a key role in the algorithm development for the challenge, in addition to using suitable AI approaches for the actual classification task. This challenge is organised by the ODELIA project, a pan-European consortium building a software framework for swarm learning to develop the

first clinically useful AI algorithm for the detection of breast cancer in MRI.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

MRI, Breast cancer, Classification, Multi-centre, Heterogeneity

Year

The challenge will take place in 2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge focuses on the diagnosis of breast cancer MRI images, making a large set of MRI scans (for 500 patients) publicly available. The main characteristic that defines its novelty is the heterogeneity of such a dataset (mimicking a real-world dataset with images from 6 different centres in 5 European countries) that will include pre and post-contrast sequences. Hence, we expect that novel solutions for pre-processing of the training dataset will play a key role in the algorithm development for the challenge, an aspect often not considered in challenges.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The task of the challenge (breast cancer classification of MRI images) has an extraordinary clinical potential to help in breast cancer screening, reducing the processing time of the images and therefore making reporting accessible earlier. In addition, after the challenge, the algorithms of the top five teams will be tested in the ODELIA SL implementation.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

We have also submitted an application for a workshop (satellite event) and we would like the challenge to be part of it. The workshop is Deep-Breath 2025: 2nd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care, <https://deep-breath-miccai.github.io/deepbreath-2025> (members of our challenge organising team are also part of the workshop organisation)

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

2 hours would be enough to accommodate talks of the top 5 teams and a summary one (15+5 min each).

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect 50 participant teams, based on the number of participants in similar challenges

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to coordinate a joint publication of the results of the top 5 winners of the challenge. This publication will be coordinated by the challenge organising team.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

During the challenge, online: using the Grand Challenge platform (already in contact with them and preparing the corresponding application). At the conference, normal presentation infrastructure (projector, microphones, etc) will be fine.

TASK 1: ODELIA 2025: Breast Cancer Classification on MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The ODELIA consortium organising this challenge is committed to detect breast cancer early and accurately. Given the recent recommendations of using breast MRI as an additional screening tool for women at high risk and with dense breast tissue, we believe there is a need for the cancer research community to develop AI-based automated algorithms to detect breast cancer using the large volume of data produced through MRI imaging. Such methods will have the potential to support radiologists in breast MRI interpretation and classification, and to help detect cancer earlier.

The aim of the challenge is to diagnose and classify breast cancer on MRI images. Each MRI study (one per patient) is assigned two labels, one for the left breast and one for the right breast. Each breast must be categorized into one of three classes/labels: "no lesion," "benign lesion" or "malignant lesion." In addition to the inherent difficulty of distinguishing between these classes, another challenge of the task is the heterogeneity of the data set. Protocols, scanner manufacturers, and reconstruction settings differ as MRI scans originate from multiple centers and countries. This presents unique challenges for technical development, as the variability will increase the complexity in model training and optimisation. However, this heterogeneity is of high value for researchers, as it allows them to assess whether the developed models can generalise effectively and be applied in realistic clinical settings.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

MRI, Breast cancer, Classification, Multi-centre, Heterogeneity

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Dr Lorena Escudero Sánchez, University of Cambridge, UK

Dr Gustav Müller-Franzes, Aachen University Hospital, Germany

Dr Oliver Saldanha, TU Dresden, Germany

Dr Nicholas Payne, University of Cambridge, UK

Dr Kamarul bin Abdullah, University of Cambridge, UK

Dr Tianyu Zhang, Radboud University, Netherlands

Dr Wouter Veldhuis, University Medical Center Utrecht, Netherlands

Dr Markus Wenzel, Fraunhofer Institute for Digital Medicine MEVIS, Germany

Dr Lars Ole Schwen, Fraunhofer Institute for Digital Medicine MEVIS, Germany

Mr Michael Kalogeropoulos, Hygeia Hospital, Greece

Mr Aitor López López, Ribera Salud Hospital, Spain

Mr Alfredo Miguel Soro Busto, Ribera Salud Hospital, Spain

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

All communications should be through the dedicated email address of the challenge:

odeliachallenge2025@gmail.com

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025 conference and Deep-Breath 2025 workshop.

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Grand Challenge (grand-challenge.org). We are already in communication with the Grand Challenge support team and will be submitting our application to their platform alongside this application.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Not available yet, will be created as part of the grand-challenge.org webpage

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide a cash award of 1,000€ for the winner.

The organisers and members of the ODELIA project may not participate in the challenge. Members of the organisers' institutes or collaborators of the ODELIA consortium may participate but will not be eligible for awards and will not be listed in the leaderboard.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 5 methods will be announced publicly, and their results will be presented during the MICCAI 2025 conference and included in the summary/review paper. They will be required to share their code so it can be tested and validated before announcing the winners.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An embargo time will apply, to ensure that the general overall publication describing the purpose and top results of the challenge can be published first. The top 5 teams, with up to 2 authors per team, will be included as co-authors of this publication, with the rest listed as "ODELIA Challenge group", following, e.g., <https://doi.org/gjxt dw>.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission (type 2) on Grand Challenge. Participants will also have to submit an abstract (approximately 3 pages) describing their method, including details of the versions used, and training results prior to submission of final results. The top 5 teams will be required to also share their complete code with the challenge organisers.

Only the provided training data and publicly available (e.g., accessible without restriction, CC-BY-NC-SA equivalent or more permissive) datasets and/or pre-trained models are allowed. Participants need to declare which publicly available datasets and/or models have been used for training in their abstract with the phase one submission to the challenge. No other (i.e. non publicly available) pre-trained models or datasets can be used.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to

compute challenge results.

The challenge will run in two phases. During the first phase, teams can submit a maximum of 3 times per team testing their submission on a small set of 50 images from the test dataset (more details below). Successful submission to the first phase, which includes an abstract describing the methodology and training results, will be a requirement for the final submission (second phase) that will be limited to one submission per team.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release of training data: 1st of May

Intention to submit/first phase submission: 1st of July

Final submission: 15th of July

Evaluation and results (including receiving and checking code of top 5 teams): 15th of August

Challenge Day: during the MICCAI Conference (23-27th September), during the Deep-Breath workshop day

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval has been obtained from each of the relevant centres to allow the data to be used for the public challenge. These are the details of each one of the ethics approval, and corresponding documents can also be shared if needed:

-CAM (UK): 1) IRAS Project ID 122652, 2) IRAS Project ID 251317, 3) IRAS Project ID 143891, 4) IRAS Project ID 260281

-MHA (Greece): local approval received by letter on January 30th, 2023 (no number)

-RSH (Spain): Local ID 23/430-E

-RUMC (Netherlands): Local ID 2024-17192

-UKA (Germany): Local ID EK 24-087 (23-006)

-UMCU (Netherlands): Confirmation that no further approval was required received by email on the 5th of March 2024 (no number).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organisers will provide an example script for pre-processing of the images and the script for computing metrics and rankings through the GrandChallenge platform.

Specifically, the structured pipeline defined by our example pre-processing script follows these steps to ensure consistency across scans:

- Resampling the images to a target voxel spacing of (0.7, 0.7, 3) mm.
- Cropping or padding each scan to a fixed shape of (512, 512, 32) using mean padding.
- Standardizing orientation using `tio.ToCanonical()`.
- Automatically cropping the height of the scan to 256 voxels, ensuring the breast region is preserved based on intensity localization.
- Splitting the scan into left and right breast images using spatial cropping.
- Saving the processed images in a structured output directory.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Each team participating in the challenge must submit a Docker image producing results on the test dataset cases. The Docker images will not be shared by the organisers. Each team participating in the final phase must also write a short abstract (3 pages) describing the method used, if any other publicly available data has been used and their training results. The top 5 winners agree to provide their code to the organizers. Generally participants are encouraged to make their code available as open source.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There are no conflicts of interest. Before and during the challenge, only the organising team will have access to the images and labels in the test set.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening,Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Women in breast cancer screening programmes that include MRI or cancer diagnosis pathways using MRI. Although the dataset (challenge cohort) is a retrospective study, the target cohort will be prospective, i.e., women in such screening programmes that include MRI in the future.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Roughly half of the cases included in the 6 datasets collected for this challenge correspond to women who have undergone MRI imaging as part of a screening programme, and the other half are women whose MRI scans have been taken as part of a cancer diagnosis pathway (suspected cancer, MRI imaging as a diagnostic tool). The population included in the challenge cohort is therefore a sample from the screened/pathway populations. More details can be found in the table included as attachment to this proposal.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The images will be given as NIfTI files containing all 2D slices of various sequences of the MRI scan, including one for pre-contrast and two or more post-contrast ones. The corresponding information about the sequence will be provided, along with the labels for training, divided per case (i.e., patient) and into left and right breast labels (i.e., two labels per patient).

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information related to the patients themselves will be provided as the aim is for the methods to detect cancer from the images alone, i.e., irrespective of age, etc.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The images correspond to the breast/chest region, shown in MRI data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm should target lesions in the breast that are either benign or malignant (breast cancer), proven through histopathology and/or follow up (benign) as described below (in annotations questions).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

We will use three metrics: AUC, Specificity (at 90% sensitivity) and Sensitivity (at 90% specificity) We will obtain three separate rankings for all teams and we will then compute the average of these rankings to determine the final ranking of all teams. The average scoring will be computed by averaging the raw ranks of the three metrics. If a tie-breaker occurs, the highest AUC score will be used to rank tied teams. (See description and justification of metrics in a later question)

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The whole training + testing dataset is integrated by seven independent datasets from six centres in five different countries. Three of them were acquired with Philips machines, two with GE and two with Siemens. The cases have been acquired with fat suppression (Fat-sat) and without (Non-fat-sat). More information can be found in the table in attachment. A figure also in attachment shows the split of each dataset in terms of the three labels..

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Imaging modalities will include pre-contrast MRI scan together with several post-contrast scans acquired during the different phases of the patient studies. Such images will come from a set of diverse commercial, modern scanners available at the different collection sites but they follow the general standard breast MRI acquisition protocol defined by the WWO for breast cancer screening (<https://www.ohsu.edu/school-of-medicine/diagnostic-radiology/mr-bilateral-breasts-wwo-protocol>), or a similar internal one.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

CAM: Cambridge University Hospitals, UK (2 different datasets)

UKA: Aachen University Hospital, Germany

UMCU: University Medical Center Utrecht, Netherlands

RUMC: Radboud University, Netherlands

RSH: Ribera Salud Hospital, Spain

MHA: Hygeia Hospital, Greece

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical teams that include expert radiologists have been involved in the data acquisition in each centre.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case in this challenge means one complete set of MRI images for one specific patient, including both breasts, i.e. algorithms should generate two labels per case, one for the left and right breast respectively, that will be considered equally to calculate metrics. Each case will contain both pre and post-contrast images (sequences) at one time-point (imaging session).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training dataset (publicly available) will contain 500 cases. The training dataset will be published in Zenodo, so it will remain publicly accessible to researchers after the challenge closes. We are also preparing a manuscript describing this dataset to be published at the same time.

The test dataset will contain between 200 and 350 cases (final quality checks are currently being performed on the datasets). The test dataset will contain two separate subsets. The first one will be drawn from the same datasets conforming to the training dataset, therefore having a similar distribution of acquisition and reconstruction settings, ensuring that the distribution of labels (no lesion, benign and malignant) represents also to the distribution observed in the training dataset. In addition, the second test dataset will correspond to one (or more) centres that will be reserved completely for testing only, i.e., no images included in the training dataset, in order to measure the generalisability of the algorithms, a key aspect of this challenge.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The training dataset, for the purpose of training and validation, will correspond to approximately 80% of the cases of each centre contributing to the training dataset and will have a total of 500 cases. Approximately 20% of the cases from each of those sites will be used collectively as a test dataset. Additionally, one more test dataset (from one or two centres) will be reserved completely for testing purposes. The teams can choose how they split the training dataset into training and validation, or to use cross validation in their training to assess the performance of their algorithms.

The proportion of the different classes (i.e., distribution of benign and malignant lesions) matches the expected

occurrence rate in a realistic clinical setting.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The dataset is a real world dataset, corresponding to MRI images from different centres and countries, with a heterogeneous composition of vendors/manufacturers, as well as imaging protocols and other acquisition parameters.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data will be new data, published just in advance for the challenge, so it will be seen for the first time at the time of the challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The ground truth for each case was established based on pathology or 2-year follow-up for benign cases, ensuring a high-quality, objective standard that supersedes individual radiological interpretations and minimizes the impact of inter-rater variability.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

It was firstly agreed between the clinical experts in the ODELIA consortium the precise meaning of the three labels provided, described below, and this definition was used to create the annotations based on ground truth.. The same procedure was followed for all cases (training and testing).

- Malignant lesion: lesion with enhancement observed and proven to be malignant with either histopathology or follow up information. Non mass enhancement proven to be malignant.

- Benign lesion: well-defined lesion with enhancement observed and proven to not to be malignant with either histopathology or follow up information.

- No lesion: none of the lesions described above are present.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None, annotations were done by a human expert: they are generated in the clinical routine by expert radiologists/oncologists for diagnosis purposes.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A, only one annotation is given per case and breast. If multiple lesions appear in one breast, only the worst label is provided (e.g. only malignant if both malignant and benign lesions are present).

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Given the heterogeneity of the dataset, we expect pre-processing to be a key step for participant teams to investigate and choose. The organisers will provide an example pre-processing script, so participant teams should either develop their own pre-processing or they can use the example one. This aspect will be clearly stated in the challenge description on its website.

Specifically, the structured pipeline defined by our example pre-processing script follows these steps to ensure consistency across scans:

- Resampling the images to a target voxel spacing of (0.7, 0.7, 3) mm.
- Cropping or padding each scan to a fixed shape of (512, 512, 32) using mean padding.
- Standardizing orientation using `tio.ToCanonical()`.
- Automatically cropping the height of the scan to 256 voxels, ensuring the breast region is preserved based on intensity localization.
- Splitting the scan into left and right breast images using spatial cropping.
- Saving the processed images in a structured output directory.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The ground truth for each case was established based on pathology or 2-year follow-up for benign cases, ensuring a high-quality, objective standard that supersedes individual radiological interpretations and minimizes the impact of inter-rater variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

As previously mentioned, the metrics that will be used are AUC, Specificity (at 90% sensitivity) and Sensitivity (at 90% specificity). Each metric will consider, equally, two labels per case, for the left and right breasts. Rankings will be calculated for each one of the metrics and combined as an average ranking using the three metrics. The average scoring will be computed by averaging the raw ranks of the three metrics. If a tie-breaker occurs, the highest AUC score will be used to rank tied teams. The average rankings will be calculated for each one of the test

datasets (in-distribution vs independent test datasets) and the final winners will be selected taking into account both of them.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

- AUC: in multi-classification problems, the AUC is commonly used as a way of synthesising the relevant information about precision and recall of the algorithm performance for different thresholds. This metric then becomes useful particularly when there is an imbalance distribution between classes, as it is the case in our task.
- Sensitivity (at 90% Specificity): In screening, it's vital to minimize false positives to avoid unnecessary anxiety and interventions. By fixing specificity at 90%—meaning 90% of non-cancer cases are correctly identified—we assess how well the method detects cancer cases under this controlled rate of false positives. This is especially important for routine screening in populations with a lower prevalence of disease.
- Specificity (at 90% Sensitivity): In high-risk groups, ensuring that most cancers are detected is paramount. Here, sensitivity is set at 90%, ensuring that 90% of actual cancer cases are caught, and then specificity is measured to see how well the method avoids misclassifying healthy cases. This balance is crucial when screening high-risk patients, where missing a cancer diagnosis can have severe consequences.

AUC is commonly used in classification problems, including breast cancer (some examples are doi: 10.1177/15330338221087828 and doi: 10.3389/fonc.2022.1042964). Specificity (at 90% sensitivity) and Sensitivity (at 90% specificity) are metrics well aligned with the typical metrics used in clinical settings and therefore easier to interpret for clinical and non-technical experts. We are confident that introducing these metrics will fit the purpose of our challenge.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The chosen metrics and their associated ranks will be used in conjunction. This decision is justified by their ability to capture the key aspects of the problem domain (multi-class, imbalanced classification). Additionally, the use of ranks allows for a fairer comparison between teams, as it takes into account the relative performance of each team on each task. The average scoring will be computed by averaging the raw ranks of the three metrics. If a tie-breaker occurs, the highest AUC score will be used to rank tied teams.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Only full working submissions will be considered. Teams will have three attempts during phase 1 to test their submissions on a subset of 50 cases of the test dataset, that will be chosen to contain outliers or extreme examples of the dataset (largest cases, smallest cases, diverse image quality, etc.) for participants to check their algorithms work in those cases, in addition to average cases. A subset of the hidden cases will also be part of this phase-1 subset. These 50 cases will also be part of the phase-2 testing dataset.

A successful submission to the first phase on this subset of the test dataset will be required to make a final submission.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The AUC, Specificity (at 90% sensitivity) and Sensitivity (at 90% specificity) will be calculated for all test cases, and three ranks (one per metric) will be computed. By combining the three scores we are able not only to consider the

performance of the algorithms on the test dataset, but also to assess their performance based on the clinical significance of errors or mislabelling of the different classes. The task rank will be calculated as the average of the ranks for each score.

The average ranking will be obtained for the two test datasets (in-distribution vs independent). Top performing teams for each test dataset will be considered, and a combination of both (average ranks) will be used to decide the final leaderboard of the challenge.

A leaderboard will also be created for phase 1, so teams can make sure their algorithms run within the platform and no issues appear when facing the example test dataset cases (particularly extreme and hidden cases), but to also check how their performance ranks globally with respect to other teams. We believe this can be useful for teams not to be discouraged if for example they achieve a seemingly low performance on the 50 phase 1 cases, but to have a more objective understanding of their performance in global terms by comparison with other teams. The final leaderboard will be made available before the conference, in particular to organise with the top teams their attendance to the event.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Similarly to the approach used in recent challenges (e.g., Endoscopic Vision Challenge), we will use bootstrapping to determine the stability of the rankings and the significance of the difference in performance, according to our metrics, of the different algorithms. In addition, a Wilcoxon signed rank test will be used to perform a paired comparison between the proportion of the winner remaining the winner. The statistical analysis will be done with our own python script, written and cross-checked by the technical members of the consortium (engineers and physicists).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Bootstrapping (with additional Wilcoxon test) was identified by Maier-Hein et al. in

“Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care” (see references) as an appropriate tool to determine rank variability.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

For the top winners, once their code is shared, we will be able to compute the average inference time and add this information to the paper, in line with sustainability concerns, recent focus of the AI community. The inference time per case will be limited by the platform infrastructure/limitations to 5 minutes, but teams should try their algorithms to be in line with realistic clinical practices and have a maximum of 1-2 minutes inference running time. This aspect will be specified in the challenge information and teams need to take it into account.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

ODELIA Project: <https://odelia.ai/>

Breat cancer statistics: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer>

EUSOBI guidelines on breast MRI: Clauser P, Mann R, Athanasiou A, Prosch H, Pinker K, Dietzel M, Helbich TH, Fuchsjaeger M, Camps-Herrero J, Sardanelli F, Forrai G, Baltzer PAT. A survey by the European Society of Breast Imaging on the utilisation of breast MRI in clinical practice. *Eur Radiol.* 2018 May;28(5):1909-1918. doi: 10.1007/s00330-017-5121-4. Epub 2017 Nov 22. PMID: 29168005; PMCID: PMC5882636.

MRI screening for women with dense breast tissue: Bakker MF, de Lange SV, Pijnappel RM, Mann RM, Peeters PHM, Monninkhof EM, et al. Supplemental MRI Screening for Women with Extremely Dense Breast Tissue. *N Engl J Med.* 2019;381(22):2091-102.

Metrics for Multi-class Classification: an Overview, Grandini M, Bagli E and Visani G, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2008.05756>

Statistical analysis: Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. *Nat Commun* 9, 5217 (2018).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07619-7>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A